

HEARING, FEELING, SEEING: IMPRESSIONISTIC DOMINANCE OF JOSEPH CONRAD'S PROSE WORKS

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ABSTRACT. The paper examines the prevalence of impressionism as a dominant stylistic element in Joseph Conrad's prose. It highlights how impressionism deviated significantly from traditional artistic standards by prioritising intuitive perception and immediate impressions. Joseph

Conrad, recognised for his distinctive literary contributions, is esteemed as a pioneer of literary impressionism. Though Conrad never explicitly self-identified as an impressionist, his association with the movement became evident posthumously, largely due to critical analyses by Ford M. Ford. The text elucidates Conrad's evolving attitude towards impressionism, from initial scepticism to eventual recognition. While Conrad avoids direct discussion of impressionism, he emphasises the crucial role of sensory impressions in evoking emotional responses from readers. Conrad's literary style resonates with impressionism's ethos, characterised by meticulous attention to detail and skillful use of narrative techniques such as point of view.

Through this technique, Conrad intricately integrates various perspectives, slowing the pace of plot development and highlighting the narrative's psychological aspects. Additionally, Conrad's adept depiction of landscapes showcases his artistic talent, as he effectively employs language to evoke mood and sentiment. Moreover, Conrad's thematic exploration of the relativity of human concepts and the inherent impossibility of attaining absolute truths challenges entrenched societal norms and values. Essentially, Conrad's «instinctive impressionism» permeates his literary body of work, evident in his fondness for sensory impressions, nuanced psychological

portrayals, and the exploration of universal truths. Through his works, Conrad appeals to readers capable of discerning and appreciating the subtle emotional intricacies present within characters and their surrounding environment.

KEYWORDS: impression, style, narrative, novel, technique, perspective, sensory.

Joseph Conrad, renowned for his intricate narratives and profound exploration of the human psyche, stands as a pivotal figure in the annals of English literature. Amidst the myriad of critical lenses through which Conrad's works have been analysed, the lens of impressionism emerges as particularly illuminating. In this thesis, we delve into the notion of impressionistic dominance within Conrad's prose, unravelling its significance and implications for understanding his literary oeuvre.

Central to this exploration is the concept of impressionism, a movement that burgeoned in the late 19th century and found expression across various art forms, including literature. This testified to a radical revolution in the consciousness of young artists who sought change and freedom of expression. Emerging as a reaction against the rigidity of realism, impressionism sought to capture the fleeting essence of moments, privileging subjective perception over objective representation. As we embark on this journey through Conrad's works, we confront the interplay between impressionistic techniques and thematic motifs, elucidating the ways in which Conrad's prose transcends mere narrative to evoke visceral impressions in the reader.

Conrad's name in the literary world began to be associated with impressionism only after his death, thanks to the critical essays-remiscences of his associate, writer, and essayist, Ford M. Ford, who declared Conrad, along with Henry James and Stephen Crane, iconic figures in impressionism. It is noteworthy that Conrad never considered himself an impressionist. During his life, his attitude towards this artistic movement evolved from scepticism and reticence to recognition. Conrad does not write directly about impressionism as a phenomenon. However, he notes that only through the depiction of sensory impressions can the writer evoke the appropriate emotions in readers. Conrad sets himself the task of using «*the power of the printed word to make*»

readers hear, feel, and, «*before all, to make*» them «*see*», and he highlights the last word in italics because «*seeing*» for him means penetrating the deep essence of things. The author adds: «*That –and no more, and it is everything*» (Conrad, 1914). It should be noted that a similar opinion was expressed by Frenchmen Edmond and Jules de Goncourt: «*Seeing, feeling, expressing – this is all art*» (Halych, 2001, p. 397). In the end, the writer calls himself an «*instinctive impressionist*» (Saunders, p. 1899), dissociating himself from the official representatives of the school with these words and emphasizing the inadvertence and spontaneity of impressionistic features presented in his prose, which can be considered at the same time as a statement of his involvement in this art.

For Conrad, as for the impressionists, the basic knowledge of reality is the direct perception of the surrounding world in a set of visual, auditory, and tactile impressions that arise instantly and spontaneously. Hence the extensive use of minor details, strokes, and shades that, like the blurred strokes of impressionist artists, convey the narrator's mood and feeling when contemplating phenomena and objects. At the same time, the plot loses its dynamism; the general outline of the events looks loose and vague. This approach is strengthened by introducing «point of view» techniques that presuppose considering the same phenomenon from the characters' positions and their unique vision. Thus, in the novel «Lord Jim», the tragic situation on the ship is presented through the eyes of Captain Marlowe, Lieutenant Brown, and Brierley, each of whom has his point of view on Jim and his actions. In the process of narration, the eyewitnesses not only express what they heard or saw but also allow the reader to experience everything with them. In this way, the work builds a complex system of psychological digressions that slow down the development of the plot line. This author's approach is thoughtful; for him, not the order of the events but how and why they happen is essential.

To achieve the effect of the immediacy of impressions, Conrad resorts to the structural technique of framing: the narrator conveys the story told to him by another person. In the novel «Heart of Darkness», such a character is Marlowe, the sailor travelling on a tropical river. Reflections and assessments of an eyewitness endowed

with subtle intuition and observation are presented in the spirit of impressionistic writing, with emphasis on details and nuances that reflect the state of the hero in moments of greatest emotional upheaval.

Conrad's impressionistic manner was clearly manifested in describing the landscapes. Here he achieved the skill and sophistication of a true artist, thinking of every word and bringing the phrase to perfection. The author uses such means as the play of colours, tinted hints, highlights, contrasts, etc. The depiction of nature in Impressionist literature seamlessly intertwines with the consciousness of the observer, presenting a unified whole. For the Impressionist, the significance lies not in the objective reality of the world but rather in the mood and the most delicate emotions evoked within the individual during moments of contemplation. In Joseph Conrad's «Lord Jim», this symbiotic relationship is eloquently portrayed when Jim's heart is suffused with tranquilly, assurance, and a sense of boundless security as he beholds the serene nocturnal scene from the ship's bridge. Conrad skillfully parallels this experience to the love etched on a mother's face, underscoring the profound emotional resonance that nature's beauty elicits within the human spirit: «*A marvellous stillness pervaded the world, and the stars, together with the serenity of their rays, seemed to shed upon the earth the assurance of everlasting security. The young moon recurved, and shining low in the west, was like a slender shaving thrown up from a bar of gold, and the Arabian Sea, smooth and cool to the eye like a sheet of ice, extended its perfect level to the perfect circle of a dark horizon*» (Conrad, 1931, p. 17). Nature, akin to art, serves as a refuge for Conrad's protagonists, offering sanctuary from the harsh realities of the world and instilling a profound sense of spiritual equilibrium.

Thus, building upon the impressionist principle of artistic comprehension as the culmination of subjective impressions within temporal and spatial contexts, Conrad espouses a view regarding the relative nature of human perceptions of reality and the inaccessibility of absolute truth. This perspective inherently challenges the validity of societal norms and values. Overall, Conrad's impressionistic approach aligns with his aim of writing for readers capable of not only looking but truly «seeing», encompassing both the characters within his novels, the broader readership, and the world at large.

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